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ANALYSIS OF METHODS OF TREATMENT OF EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes the literature on the problem of treatment of exudative otitis media. Exudative otitis media is a polyetiologic inflammatory disease of the middle ear, in the etiopathogenesis of which the dysfunction of the auditory tube plays a key role. The pathomorphologic substrate of exudative otitis media is chronic catarrhal inflammation of the mucous membrane mainly of the meso-, hypotympanum and auditory tube, and clinical signs are the presence of exudate in the tympanic cavity, absence of signs of acute inflammation and defect of the tympanic membrane. The most common cause of exudative otitis media is respiratory viral infections, the second cause is acute otitis media. The prevalence of exudative otitis media depends on age and, according to various authors, is up to 35% in children of the 1st year of life; 3-5 years - 10-30%; 6-7 years - 3-10%; 9-10 years - 1-3%. Exudative otitis media is the most frequent cause of hearing loss in children aged 2 to 7 years - during mass examinations of children it is found in 30.2% of cases. Studies by foreign authors confirm the independent resolution of most cases of exudative otitis media, otherwise patients need treatment. Modern medicine considers many treatment options for exudative otitis media, up to the alternative of using hearing aids for patients with contraindications to other types of treatment. In a number of countries, in the diagnosis of exudative average otitis media, it often prescribes medicines or surgical treatment of patients without active observation.

Key words: exudative otitis media, treatment tactics, tympanotomy.

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье анализируется литература о проблеме лечения экссудативного среднего отита. Среда экссудативного отита представляет собой полиэтиологическое воспалительное заболевание среднего уха, в этиопатогенезе, из которого играет дисфункция слуховой трубки. Патоморфологический субстрат экссудативного среднего отита - это хроническое воспаление слизистой оболочки, в основном мезо-, гипотимпанума и слуховой трубки, а клинические признаки являются присутствием экссудата в барабанной полости, отсутствие признаков острой воспаления и дефекта барабанной перепонки. Наиболее распространенной причиной экссудативного среднего отита является респираторное вирусное инфекции, второй причиной является острый средний отит. Распространенность экссудативного среднего отита зависит от возраста и, по мнению различных авторов, составляет до 35% у детей 1-го года жизни; 3-5 лет-10-30%; 6-7 лет-3-10%; 9-10 лет-1-3%. Среда экссудативного отита является наиболее частой причиной потери слуха у детей в возрасте от 2 до 7 лет - во время массовых исследований детей она обнаруживается в 30,2% случаев. Исследования, проведенные иностранными авторами, подтверждают независимое разрешение большинства случаев экссудативного среднего отита, в противном случае пациенты нуждаются в лечении. Современная медицина рассматривает многие варианты лечения для экссудативного среднего отита, в зависимости от альтернативы использования слуховых аппаратов для пациентов с противопоказаниями для других типов лечения. В ряде стран, при диагностике экссудативного среднего отита, часто назначает лекарства или хирургическое лечение пациентам без активного наблюдения.

Ключевые слова: экссудативная среда отит, тактика лечения, тимпаностомия

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EKSSUDATIV O'RTA OTIT DAVOLASH USULLARINI TAHLIL QILISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ekssudativ o'rta otitni davolash muammosi bo'yicha adabiyotlar tahlil qilinadi. Ekssudativ otit muhiti o'rta quloqning polietiologik yallig'lanish kasalligi bo'lib, uning etiopatogenezida eshitish naychasi disfunktsiyasi ishtirok etadi. Ekssudativ o'rta otitning patomorfologik substrati shilliq qavatning surunkali yallig'lanishi, asosan mezo-, gipotimpanum va eshituv nayining yallig'lanishi bo'lib, klinik belgilari nog'ora bo'shlig'ida ekssudatning mavjudligi, nog'ora pardaning o'tkir yallig'lanish va nuqson belgilarining yo'qligi hisoblanadi. Ekssudativ o'rta otitning eng keng tarqalgan sababi respirator virusli infeksiya, ikkinchi sababi o'tkir o'rta otitdir. Ekssudativ o'rta otitning tarqalishi yoshga bog'liq bo'lib, turli mualliflarning fikriga ko'ra, 1 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarda 35% gacha; 3-5-yil - 10-30%; 6-7 yoshda - 3-10%; 9-10-yil-1-3%. Ekssudativ otit 2 yoshdan 7 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarda eshitish qobiliyatini yo'qotishning eng keng tarqalgan sababi hisoblanadi - bolalarni ommaviy tekshirish paytida u 30,2% hollarda aniqlanadi. Chet el olimlarining tadqiqotlari shuni ko'rsatadiki, ekssudativ o'rta otitning aksariyat holatlari o'z-o'zidan tuzaladi, aks holda bemorlar davolanishga muhtoj bo'ladi. Zamonaviy tibbiyot ekssudativ o'rta otitni davolashning turli usullarini taklif qiladi, jumladan boshqa turdagi davolash usullari qo'llab bo'lmaydigan bemorlar uchun eshitish moslamalaridan foydalanish imkoniyatini ham ko'rib chiqadi. Ba'zi mamlakatlarda ekssudativ o'rta otit tashxisi qo'yilganda, ko'pincha bemorlarni faol kuzatuvga olmasdan, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri dori-darmon yoki jarrohlik yo'li bilan davolash tayinlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekssudativ muhit, davolash taktikasi, timpanostomiya.

The World Health Organization predicts that by 2030 the number of people with socially significant hearing defects will increase by more than 30% [6]. At least 30% of all cases of hearing loss are caused by middle ear pathology. In recent decades, many authors have noted an increase in the incidence of exudative otitis media (ESO), with it accounting for 15-17% of all ear diseases [7]. Epidemiologic studies show that ESO affects 50-80% of children under 5 years of age [8,9], two out of 1000 children have serious complications. As a result, they endure radical middle ear surgeries that reduce the quality of life of the child, who subsequently needs social adaptation [10,11]. This confirms the seriousness of the problem of ESO and brings this pathology to the forefront both in the country and in the world as a whole [7,12].

In the scientific medical literature, exudative otitis media has a number of other names. Often the name depends on the physician-researcher's view of the causal role of one or another factor in the stages of disease development. A number of physicians emphasize the main role of auditory tube obstruction in the development of the disease and use such terms as "pharyngotubotympanal disease", "chronic tubal obstruction", "tubotympanal catarrh", "tubotympanitis", "otosalpingitis" (2,3.). At the same time, other otorhinolaryngologists adhere to the point of view of the root cause of this disease in the role of vacuum in the formation of liquid sterile content in the middle ear, sweating through the capillary wall, which gave rise to another kind of names "middle ear hydrocele", "hydrotympaanum", "serotympaanum", "serous otitis media", "simple serous otitis media", "sterile middle otitis media", etc. (4,5). In turn, other names of this pathology are associated with the discharge of inflammatory exudate into the tympanic cavity, so the disease is called exudative otitis media, exudative catarrhal otitis media, otitis media with exudate, etc. (8).

The terms "secretory catarrh of the middle ear" and "secretory otitis media" have been proposed to emphasize the increased secretory activity of the mucous glands of the middle ear mucosa, and to designate forms of this pathology with sticky, viscous contents - "glue ear" (glueear), "mucoïd ear", "seromucoid catarrh of the middle ear", viscous contents - "glue

ear" (glueear), "mucoïd ear", "seromucoid catarrh of the middle ear" (5,6) Hemorrhagic forms of otitis media are designated as idiopathic hematotympanum, or hemorrhagic serous otitis media (6.). Diagnoses that define a mild, superficial form of middle ear mucosal disease are used: "acute nonpurulent middle otitis media," "catarrhal otitis media," "catarrh of the auditory tube and middle ear," "simple middle otitis media," "difficult catarrh," etc. (7).

In Western scientific and medical literature, the term "serous otitis media" is most often used, which characterizes a mild, initial form of the disease and is based on serous inflammation of the middle ear mucosa. In the literature of European countries, the name "secretory otitis media" is used, meaning superficial inflammation of the middle ear mucosa with hypersecretion of glands and increased secretory activity of bocaloid cells, which corresponds to forms with viscous contents in the tympanic cavity prevalent in children. In the CIS, including the Republic of Uzbekistan, the term "exudative otitis media" is most commonly used, emphasizing the importance of complex and deep inflammatory processes in the middle ear.

Differences in the designation of the same disease indicate that the process of the appearance of liquid, non-purulent contents in the tympanic cavity is not clear at all. In addition, there are clinical variants of the disease, in connection with which difficulties in diagnosis and treatment are not excluded. Conservative and surgical methods are used in the treatment of ESO. Surgical treatment of ESO is recommended in the majority of cases when conservative therapy is ineffective and when the duration of the disease is 2-4 weeks or more [13,14]. Conservative methods of treatment include: active surveillance; oral or topical administration of steroidal drugs, antibiotics, antihistamines, decongestants; and blowing of the auditory tubes. Surgical treatment methods include: paracentesis, tympanic cavity bypass (insertion of a ventilation tube) with/without simultaneous adenoidectomy in children, laser myringotomy, middle ear surgery.

Active observation (Activeobservation) is the process of regular check-ups of the patient, including evaluation of hearing and lingual development. It is a method in which no treatment is

prescribed, but the patient is constantly monitored by the attending physician. Although the patient receives regular consultations with the doctor, the choice and responsibility for treatment decisions remains with the patient or parents (if the patient is a minor). Another term previously used was dynamic monitoring or watchfulwaiting [5].

Ear tube blowing is a technique in which the Eustachian tube (the tube that connects the middle ear and the nasopharynx) is opened by increasing pressure in the nasal cavity. The technique of this method is to conduct pressurized air into the middle ear through the eustachian tube to equalize the pressure and evacuate secretion from the tympanic cavity [15]. This can be achieved by forced exhalation with closed mouth and nose, Politzer blowing of the auditory tubes, and catheterization of the auditory tubes. In the United States and in Europe, Autoinflation for the treatment of exudative otitis media, which is performed with a balloon with a nozzle, is a common method often used for the treatment of exudative otitis media in children [16].

Antibiotics, antihistamines, decongestants are prescribed by physicians in different countries on a case-by-case basis. Steroid drugs (systemic or topical) are used in order to evacuate the secretion as soon as possible and thus restore the normal functioning of the air conduction circuit [13]. Myringotomy (paracentesis, tympanotomy) is a surgical intervention in which an incision is made in the tympanic membrane for therapeutic and diagnostic purposes. The incision is made with a special needle (with a lance-shaped blade) on the posterior-lower part of the tympanic membrane, a few millimeters long. In this way it is possible to inject medication into the middle ear. Some clinics perform laser myringotomy[5].

Tympanostomy (tympanostomy, installation of ventilation tubes) is a surgical option for the treatment of exudative otitis media and is usually used in case of repeated filling of the tympanic cavity with exudate in the absence of effect after repeated tympanotomy. It consists of inserting ventilation tubes into the tympanic membrane to restore pressure and improve the exudate outflow and allows for the trans-stympanic administration of various drugs. The criteria for this intervention vary depending on the treatment protocols of the country.

In children with exudative otitis media, many countries include nasopharyngeal endoscopy to determine the degree of lymphoid hypertrophy (adenoids) in the examination protocol. If there is a blockage of lymphoid tissue at the mouth of the auditory tubes, adenoidectomy is indicated. In some cases, this operation is sufficient to restore full hearing and normal functioning of the structures of the tympanic cavity. In some cases, more often in adults, more radical surgical interventions

are performed on the middle ear to sanitize the tympanic cavity [12].

Despite the wide discussion in the literature on the etiology, diagnosis, and treatment of exudative otitis exudata, there are different views on the choice of treatment tactics [19].

In the UK, the National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE) has developed guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of exudative otitis media. The guidelines include specialist consultation, active surveillance, surgical and non-surgical intervention. According to these guidelines, patients are first consulted by a general practitioner (GP) and referred to an otorhinolaryngologist for evaluation if hearing loss is suspected, especially in children with delayed speech development. This is followed by a 3-month follow-up with the specialist. If the condition worsens and the hearing loss increases, the choice between surgical or non-surgical treatment is made depending on the patient's medical history. With non-surgical treatment, the doctor should provide information about the benefits and risks of treatment to the patient, then offer hearing aids as an alternative when surgery is contraindicated or unacceptable. Typically, a tympanotomy is performed followed by placement of ventilation tubes (shunts). In the absence of persistent and/or frequent symptoms of upper respiratory tract infections in adults, a one-stage adenoidectomy is performed. Ventilatory tubes are subsequently removed spontaneously within 6 months to 1 year, or they are removed by an otorhinolaryngologist within the same time frame. The result is monitored by repeated audiometry and tympanometry after removal of the ventilation tubes after 2 weeks and 1 month. (NICE).

Based on a number of systematic reviews in the field, it can be concluded that in the United States of America otolaryngologists are more likely to use the Watchfulwaiting strategy. That is, the patient is seen by an ENT physician for 3 months, followed by a conclusion that in the United States, otorhinolaryngologists are more likely to use a strategy of active surveillance (Watchfulwaiting). That is, within 3 months, the patient is observed by an ENT doctor with a follow-up audiogram. In the absence of positive dynamics after 3 months, patients are offered surgical treatment in the form of tympanotomy with subsequent installation of ventilation tubes (shunts). Obviously, the treatment algorithm in the USA is similar to the treatment algorithm in the United Kingdom. In America there are both traditional methods of treatment and non-traditional methods (homeopathy, manual therapy, dietary supplements), the latter of which are not welcomed [13,15]. Types of treatment for exudative otitis media are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 - Types and tactics of treatment for exudative otitis media used in the USA. Evidence-based Practice Center Systematic Review Protocol: Otitis Media with Effusion: Comparative Effectiveness of Treatments, July 30, 2012

Surgical intervention	
Myringotomy	
Installation of a tympanostomy (ventilation) tube	
Adenoidectomy with or without myringotomy	
revenge	
Medical treatment	
Antibiotics and antimicrobials	
Nasal Steroids	
Systemic Steroids	
Other types of treatment	
Purgeingstachievyh pipes	
Additional and alternative treatment	

Hearing aids
Other types of treatment

In Germany, the surgical method, tympanotomy with/without a ventilation tube, is recognized as an effective treatment. In addition to tympanotomy, simultaneous adenoidectomy is performed in children in Germany. The benefits of surgery should always outweigh the potential risks [14]. In France, Turkey, Malaysia and other developed countries, the method of active follow-up is used in patients with exudative otitis media detected for the first time, followed by surgical intervention in the absence of positive dynamics after 3 months.

We present the treatment tactics used during the initial examination by a general practitioner (pediatrician) for suspected exudative otitis media in Malaysia. According to the reflected scheme, the initial examination includes a therapeutic examination and active surveillance tactics. Upon confirmation of the diagnosis of ESO, the patient is referred for consultation to an otorhinolaryngologist, which is specialized medical care.

We also describe the tactics of managing a patient with exudative otitis media by an otorhinolaryngologist, i.e. the algorithm of actions for non-surgical and surgical types of treatment of patients diagnosed with exudative otitis media. This tactic of introducing patients with ESO has been approved by the Malaysian Ministry of health.

As conservative treatment methods in all of the above-mentioned countries, antibiotics, steroids, antihistamines, decongestants are used, individually and in combinations (for example, antibiotics + decongestants, antihistamines + steroids).

There are also randomized controlled trials indicating the absence of significant positive dynamics during ESO when using only conservative treatment methods.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, as in other CIS countries, treatment primarily begins with drug therapy in the combined and combined use of decongestants, antibiotics and antihistamines. In the absence of a positive effect, surgical intervention is performed in the form of a tympanotomy with or without the installation of a ventilation tube, depending on the quality of the exudate, with simultaneous adenoidectomy in children with blockage of the mouth of the auditory tubes. Transstympanic administration of steroid drugs to patients after tympanotomy and/or without a ventilation tube is considered effective, which contributes to the early restoration of middle ear function.

This analysis does not include patients with exudative otitis media with concomitant hereditary diseases such as Down syndrome and congenital cleft palate (cleft lip, cleft palate). Thus, based on the analysis of the literature, it can be noted that some of the commonly used treatment methods are: active monitoring, self-filling method, antibiotics, antihistamines, decongestants, steroid medications (systemic or topical), myringotomy (paracentesis, tympanotomy), bypass surgery of the tympanic cavity.

Treatment tactics are constantly changing and improving, striving for more progressive methods. The choice of treatment tactics for exudative otitis media depends on the diagnostic and treatment protocol followed by the country. Summarizing the above, it is worth paying attention to the fact that otorhinolaryngologists from different countries do not have a single point of view when choosing a treatment method for this disease.

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ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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